

The Marketing Challenges of Pharmaceutical Industry of Bangladesh: TRIPS Review

Mohammad Abul Kashem

Abstract:

TRIPS is a very complex and daunting challenge for developing nations to cope up with its patent protection of pharmaceuticals. In this case, the constraints of pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh are related to lack of technical expertise; low participation on R&D; health care; limited resources; absence of supporting backward linkage & technological infrastructure; abuse of intellectual property rights; and other pressures as well. The study aims to identify the role of each of the contributing factors on TRIPS and subsequent development necessary to improvement of pharmaceutical industries of Bangladesh. That's why; 200 sample respondents were considered from the 11 pharmaceutical industries of Bangladesh and used multiple regression analysis through SPSS 22.0. Out of the factors R&D initiatives (0.667), quality & regulatory compliance (0.533), competition (0.522), raw materials source & supply (0.409), technology (0.325) and parallel import-compulsory licensing-technology transfer (0.320) are worth considerable. The contribution of those factors might instigate a sophisticated growth and development in the pharmaceutical sector.

Keyword: TRIPS, Pharmaceutical Industry, Bangladesh, R&D.

Introduction

Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS) sets the framework for future drug marketing and manufacturing in poor countries. Public health advocates, including World Health Organization (WHO) officials, contend that TRIPS and related free trade agreements containing various 'TRIPS -plus' provisions are designed to expand monopoly power and maximize profits, deepening the health gap between nations where new treatments are developed and poor regions where preventable scourges still flourish. The Agreement on Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS) of the World Trade Organization (WTO) has provided special consideration to the least developed countries (LDCs), including Bangladesh especially in pharmaceuticals, by allowing an extended transition period for 10 years (Ala, 2013).

Under the current regime, Bangladesh is free to continue to permit the importation of pharmaceuticals, and the production and sale of pharmaceuticals in the domestic market whether or not they are patented elsewhere, so long as they are not patented in Bangladesh (VanDuzer, 2003). The pushback against corporate patent regimes is just one facet of an emerging public debate about global health justice (Chen, 2013). Although WTO also inculcated to developed country members to convey know-how to LDCs for sound technological base but they believe that the treaty will rather thwart the growth of the pharmaceutical industry in many countries (Abbott, 2011; Ala, 2013; Moon, 2011). The contradictory itself retains with the TRIPS and innovation in a sense that high levels of intellectual property protection may encourage innovation in the first instance, but act as a barrier to further development of substitute technologies on the issues of price of the patented product and their accessibility. That's why; this study aims to identify the role of each of the contributing factors on TRIPS and subsequent development necessary to improvement of pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh.

Literature Review

Recent years have witnessed a renewed academics and practitioners' interest in the subject of challenges, issues and opportunities of pharmaceutical industries in developing countries. Due to this, a lot of research works have been conducted on this subject in different parts of the world. But empirical evidence on the pharmaceutical sector in general and in sample pharmaceutical industries in particular is still in its infancy in Bangladesh. The discussions made below will clearly support this assumption:

The pharmaceutical industries of developing countries do not have the necessary resources to undertake a thorough and rigorous examination of every patent application (Park, 2010). The amendments in national laws are necessitated to adopt with product patents within a given transitional period to bring the reformation in pharmaceutical industry in desired states and comparable legislative adjustments in accordance to TRIPS whereas the TRIPS agreement grants member countries a rather broad spectrum for defining their own rules for the disclosure of patents (Castro, 2011). But in this case, TRIPS gives multi-national pharmaceutical corporations (which undertake most of the research and development of new drugs) a 20 year monopoly on the production and sale of new drugs somewhat additional to GATT (McIntyre, Thiede, & Birch, 2009). So, to become TRIPS compliant, it is necessary to change patents legislation for developing countries within grace period.

Again, N. Lalitha (2002) proposed that the capacity to exploit the earlier innovations depends on the technological development of the country, capacity of the domestic industry, the market size and the type of technology. It is also alarming issue that country like India, China, Korea and Brazil have adopted process patents, and developed expertise relating to new products, which were mostly around the earlier innovations of the developed countries. Overall, patents can stimulate the inventive process by avoiding the free-rider problem, promoting investment in research and development (R&D) and encouraging diffusion of knowledge (Matthews, 2010). At the same time, patent protection almost certainly results in higher prices for new medicines. All other things being equal, higher

prices will impose burdens on public health budgets in developing countries. There is reason to doubt that the pharmaceutical companies are under-funded from lack of patent rents.

On other hand, manufacturing of pharmaceutical products are vastly dependent on imported raw materials, as almost 90% of raw materials are now being imported. This dependency on imported raw materials is resulting in increased production cost of the finished products. Ultimately the competition to offer export prize is becoming tougher, which is one of the major challenges of pharmaceutical sector of Bangladesh. The government and industry have jointly planned for the development of an “API Park” to concentrate API process development and production in a single location.

The high cost of development and rapid obsolescence may prevent the transfer of technology and the patent holder may prefer direct exploitation or import of products than transferring the technology or know-how. A sizeable level of technology currently available is due to ‘spill overs’ or developing an alternative process that is very close to the existing one. This is the reason why the actual technology in a patent is often kept as a trade secret (Correa, 2000; Mehrotra, 1989). But it leads to entering a separate licensing agreement with the innovator for the transfer of that technology. Fear of competition also dissuades the transfer of technology or demands a high royalty for the transfer, but huge royalties may have a negative impact on the expenditure on R&D.

The review of the earlier works in same subject area in Bangladesh and other parts of the world reveal that the impact of TRIPS were not examined in detail through research studies in the pharmaceutical sector of Bangladesh.

Methodology

The objective of the research is to examine the relationships among predictors and criterion variable related to pharmaceutical sector of Bangladesh in general, and TRIPS and R&D related factors in particular. The study based on quantitative view for generating credible and reliable result (Hyde, 2000) and cross-sectional study for at one point of time survey (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009) through self-administered survey for better and complete response with short period of time (Muijs, 2004). Due to absence of clear idea about population size, items-scale ratio ranged from 1:4 to 1:10 for each set of scale (Hinkin, 1995). That’s why; sample size of 200 respondents from 11 pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh was considerable for 21 items for descriptive purposes. For easy access and saving of time, money and effort, convenience sampling was considered here (Marshall, 1996). The perception survey questionnaire measured through earlier suggested measures opined by the researchers/experts and also changes made by states using a five-point closed order Likert scale, where 1 indicates that the variable is not important at all and 5 is very important with extensive support from the literature. The sample size was targeted 250 initially, 200 were selected based on avoiding missing responses.

Here the variables - R&D Initiatives (RDI), Competition (C), Raw Materials Source & Supply (RMSS), Parallel Import-Compulsory Licensing-Technology Transfer (PICLWT), Quality & Regulatory Compliance (QRC), and Technology (T) have been considered to justify the role as predictors and TRIPS as a criterion variable. Based on past literature review, the hypotheses set for analyzing the relationships were:

Hypothesis 1: There is a significant relationship between R&D initiatives and TRIPS in pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh.

Hypothesis 2: There is a significant relationship between competition and TRIPS in pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh.

Hypothesis 3: There is a significant relationship between raw materials source & supply and TRIPS in pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh.

Hypothesis 4: There is a significant relationship between parallel import, compulsory licensing, technology transfer and TRIPS in pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh.

Hypothesis 5: There is a significant relationship between quality & regulatory compliance and TRIPS in pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh.

Hypothesis 6: There is a significant relationship between technology and TRIPS in pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh.

Data analysis

To assess relationships among the studied variables the researcher has performed multiple regression analysis through SPSS 22. These analyses supposed to help to understand which model fits the data best while presenting a credible assessment on the antecedents of TRIPS on pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh.

The typical multiple linear regression is:

$$\hat{Y} = B_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + \dots + b_nX_n + e$$

Where,

\hat{Y} = Dependent Variable

B_0 = Intercept

b = Slope for any corresponding change in one unit of X.

X = Independent variable.

e = Error term (Normally distributed about a mean of zero)

The above formula can be converted as follows depending on the variables [R&D Initiatives(RDI), Competition (C), Raw Materials Source & Supply (RMSS), Parallel Import-Compulsory Licensing-Technology Transfer(PICLTT), Quality & Regulatory Compliance (QRC), Technology (T) as predictors and TRIPS as criterion variable] considered for the study:

$$\text{TRIPS} = B_0 + b_1\text{RDI} + b_2\text{C} + b_3\text{RMSS} + b_4\text{PICLTT} + b_5\text{QRC} + b_6\text{T}$$

Result

Statistical techniques were applied to assess the reliability and validity of the survey and to obtain more clarity regarding the influence of the selected variables on TRIPS .

Reliability

In measuring reliability coefficient for the different constructs were computed using the reliability procedure in SPSS 22. The reliabilities of the entire construct used in this study found to be above the standard set which is 0.70 (Nunnally, 1978). The range of Cronbach's alpha shows the reliability of the variables of research ranges from $\alpha = 0.703$ to $\alpha = 0.887$; mean scores had been computed by equally weighting the mean scores of all the relevant to each construct.

Table -1: Reliability Statistics

Items	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	Overall Cronbach's Alpha
TRIPS	.887	.795
Quality & Regulatory Compliance	.883	
Raw Materials Source & Supply	.771	
R&D Initiatives	.874	
Competition	.739	
Parallel Import-Compulsory Licensing-Technology Transfer	.721	
Technology	.703	

Table 1 shows the Cronbach's Alpha of each of the variables where the variable TRIPS has the highest alpha values and Technology has the lowest but all are within acceptable limit of 0.70.

Table#2: Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Competition	2.6231	.90048	.670	.111	.024	.221
Parallel Import, Compulsory Licensing, Technology Transfer	3.0324	.77855	.144	.111	-.084	.221
R&D Initiatives	3.2327	.49691	.467	.111	-.100	.221
Quality & Regulatory Compliance	3.5223	.75326	-.484	.111	.401	.221
Technology	2.8913	.71027	-.301	.111	-.247	.221
Raw Materials Source & Supply	3.9629	.65030	-.562	.111	.571	.221
TRIPS	3.3660	.44488	-.429	.111	.440	.221

Descriptive Statistics: The followings are the attempts undertaken to justify the result of the study:

Normality Test

With the previous set guidelines for checking normality through Skewness and Kurtosis were used where positive and negative value indicates the direction of positive and negative relations respectively (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009) and the threshold values for justification were +/- 3 and +/- 10 for Skewness and Kurtosis respectively (Kline, 2005).

Table # 2 results that the mean for raw materials source & supply (3.96) is the highest while for parallel import, compulsory licensing, technology transfer (2.62) is the lowest though highest dispersion goes with competition (0.900). The skewness and kurtosis are ranged from -0.562 and 0.670, but within the expected values of skewness and kurtosis. Hence the data is normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

To test the linear association among predictors and the degree of relationship, Pearson Correlation analysis has been used with the issue of multicollinearity having score more than +/- 0.90 (Hair, Bush & Ortinau, 2006).

Table # 3: Inter-Item Correlation Matrix

	Parallel Import, Compulsory Licensing, Technology Transfer	Competition	R&D Initiatives	Quality & Regulatory Compliance	Technology	Raw Materials Source & Supply	TRIPS
Parallel Import-Compulsory Licensing-Technology Transfer	1.000	.329	.104	.057	-.008	.008	.439
Competition	.329	1.000	.028	.048	-.062	-.106	.469
R&D Initiatives	.104	.028	1.000	.168	.424	.185	.632
Quality & Regulatory Compliance	.057	.048	.168	1.000	.433	.526	.578
Technology	-.008	-.062	.424	.433	1.000	.335	.564
Raw Materials Source & Supply	.008	-.106	.185	.526	.335	1.000	.663
TRIPS	.439	.469	.632	.578	.564	.663	1.000

From the table# 3 of inter-item correlation matrix, the highest coefficient value shown is 0.663 which is close to the limit of multicollinearity issues.

Multiple Linear Regressions

The study under Multiple Linear Regressions is perfect due to more than one independent variables and a single dependent variable (Zikmund, Babin, Carr, & Griffin, 2010). To identify the relative significance, regression coefficient is used whereas coefficient of multiple determinations (R^2) provides the true predictor of multiple regression equation (Saunders et. al., 2009). The threshold value of p is less than 0.05.

Table# 4a: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.880 ^a	.774	.771	.21293	.774	272.459	6	478	.000

Table# 4b: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	74.120	6	12.353	272.459	.000 ^b
	Residual	21.673	478	.045		
	Total	95.793	484			

a. Dependent Variable: TRIPS

b. Predictors: (Constant), Parallel Import, Compulsory Licensing, Technology Transfer, Raw Materials Source & Supply, R&D Initiatives, Competition, Technology, Quality & Regulatory Compliance

As per the table# 4a, the R^2 of the model is 0.774 means to 77.4% variation in TRIPS can be explained by the predictors (parallel import-compulsory licensing-technology transfer, raw materials source & supply, competition, quality & regulatory compliance, R&D initiatives and technology). The rest of 22.6% due to other factors' influences namely, nature of the firm, size of generic market, safety, and productivity, etc.

Now, the regression equation is:

$$\text{TRIPS} = B_0 + b_1\text{RDI} + b_2\text{C} + b_3\text{RMSS} + b_4\text{PICLTT} + b_5\text{QRC} + b_6\text{T}$$

Table # 5: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.271	.089		3.056	.002
	R&D Initiatives	.619	.022	.667	19.270	.000
	Quality & Regulatory Compliance	.538	.016	.533	15.600	.000
	Technology	.378	.017	.325	4.823	.000
	Raw Materials Source & Supply	.480	.018	.409	5.359	.000
	Competition	.517	.012	.522	8.538	.000
	Parallel Import, Compulsory Licensing, Technology Transfer	.311	.014	.320	4.717	.000

a. Dependent Variable: TRIPS

Hence, the equations valued as-

$$\text{TRIPS} = 0.271 + (0.619) \text{RDI} + (0.517) \text{C} + (0.480) \text{RMSS} + (0.311) \text{PICLTT} + (0.538) \text{QRC} + (0.378) \text{T}$$

Fig # 1: Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

The model for the chart is found to be accurate being strong correlation between the models' prediction and its actual result in the fig # 1.

Table - 6: Summary of the Multiple Regression Result

Hypothesis	β	p	Statistically supported or not.
There is a significant relationship between R&D initiatives and TRIPS in pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh	.667	.000	Supported
There is a significant relationship between quality & regulatory compliance and TRIPS in pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh	.533	.000	Supported
There is a significant relationship between competition and TRIPS in pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh	.522	.000	Supported
There is a significant relationship between parallel import, compulsory licensing, technology transfer and TRIPS in pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh	.320	.000	Supported
There is a significant relationship between raw materials source & supply and TRIPS in pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh	.409	.000	Supported
There is a significant relationship between technology and TRIPS in pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh	.325	.000	Supported

The above table (table-6) summarizes the relationship between dependent and independent variables. All other hypotheses are supported statistically and R&D initiatives (0.667) have the most significant impact on TRIPS .

Discussion and Conclusion

The study demonstrated the use of multiple regression approach as a powerful tool to identify the understanding of real influences on TRIPS particularly on the growth and development of pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh. It was found that R&D initiatives (0.667), quality & regulatory compliance (0.533), competition (0.522), raw materials source & supply (0.409), technology (0.325) and parallel import, compulsory licensing, and technology transfer (0.320) are the significant positive attitudinal factors for showing enormous influence in this study. And the most influential one where the industry should keep focus is R&D initiatives. This findings also relevant to the earlier

study of Lalitha (2002) where argued as several factors like the continuous advancement in science, new breakthroughs in bio-technology, the growing participation of the private sector in the cost intensive research and development in the knowledge based pharmaceutical sector and the relative strength demonstrated by the developing nations in adapting the results of the scientific innovations to the local environment have prompted the industrialized nations to seek stronger protection for their innovations in all the countries. Again the extensive benefit from the alternative options that set by the TRIPS are not worthwhile supporting as well because the presence of multinationals did not lead to large-scale technology transfer. It covers dispute resolution procedures, remedies, and enforcement procedures. It is not only restrict but also includes significant flexibility and helps to contribute to the promotion of technological innovation and to the dissemination and transfer of technology, to the mutual advantage of users and producers of technological knowledge in a manner that conducive to social-and-economic welfare, and to a balance of rights and obligations. In fine, this research has empirically achieved encouraging results for the pharmaceutical sector of Bangladesh and has implications for pharmaceutical policy makers and industry leaders.

References

- Abbott, Frederick M. (2011), "The Doha Declaration on the TRIPS Agreement and public health and the contradictory trend in bilateral and regional free trade agreements", Occasional paper, no. 14.
- Ala, MamunUl. (2013), "A firm-level analysis of the vulnerability of the Bangladeshi pharmaceutical industry to the TRIPS Agreement: Implications for R&D capability and technology transfer", *Procedia Economics and Finance*, No. 5, pp 30 – 39.
- Castro, Tereza De (2011), "EU-India TRIPS -plus Agreement: A Real Threat for the Developing World?" *Contemporary European Studies*, <http://www.ces.upol.cz/pic/item/pdf/62.pdf>.
- Chen, Michelle. (2013), "Patents against People: How Drug Companies Price Patients out of Survival", available at: <http://www.dissentmagazine.org/article/patents-against-people-how-drug-companies-price-patients-out-of-survival>.
- Correa, Carlos M., (2000) `Intellectual Property Rights, the WTO and Developing Countries: The TRIPS Agreement and Policy Options', Zed Books Ltd, London and Third World Network, Malaysia.
- Hair, J. F. J., Bush, R. P., &Ortinou, D. J. (2006), *Marketing Research: Within A Changing Information Environment* (3rd Ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Hinkin, T. R. (1995). A review of scale development practices in the study of organizations. *Journal of Management*, 21(5):967-988.
- Hyde, K. F. (2000), Recognizing deductive processes in qualitative research. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 3(2): 82-89.
- Kline, R. B. (2005), *Principles and Practice of Structural Equation Modeling*. (2nded.). New York: The Guilford Press.
- Lalitha, N. (2002), "TRIPS and Pharmaceutical Industry: Issues and Prospects", Gujarat Institute of Development Research, Ahmedabad, India, available at: <http://www.iprsonline.org/ictsd/docs/ResourcesHealthArticleLalitha.doc>
- Marshall, M. N. (1996), *Sampling For Qualitative Research*. *Family Practice*, 13(6): 522-526.
- Matthews, Duncan (2010), "Patents in the Global Economy", Intellectual Property Office, <http://www.ipo.gov.uk/ipresearch-pglobal-201012.pdf>
- McIntyre, D. I., Thiede, M., & Birch, S. (2009). Access as a policy-relevant concept in low-and middle-income countries. *Health Economics, Policy and Law*, 4(2), 179-193.
- Mehrotra., (1989), 'Patents Act and Technological Self-Reliance: The Indian Pharmaceutical Industry' *Economic and Political Weekly*, 24(19), P: 1059-1064.
- Moon, S (2011), "Meaningful technology transfer to the LDCs: A proposal for a monitoring mechanism for TRIPS Article 66.2", ICTSD, Geneva.
- Muijs, D. (2004). *Doing Quantitative Research in Education with SPSS*. London: SAGE publications.
- Nunnally, J. C. (1978). *Psychometric Theory*. NP: McGraw-Hill.
- Park, Chan (2010), "Challenging pharmaceutical Patents: The Case of India", *Intellectual Property and Access to Medicines: Papers and Perspectives*, WHO Regional Office for South-East Asia, India, No. 9, p. 108.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P., &Thornhill, A. (2009),*Research Methods For Business Students*. (5th Ed.). Harlow, UK: Pearson Education.
- VanDuzer, Tony. (2003), "TRIPS and the Pharmaceutical Industry in Bangladesh: Towards a National Strategy", CPD Occasional Paper Series, Centre for Policy Dialogue, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
- Zikmund, W. G., Babin, B. J., Carr, J. C., & Griffin, M. (2010).*Business Research Methods*. (8th ed.). Canada: South-Western, Cengage Learning.